

SATICE

Arctic Ocean Sea-Ice and Ocean Circulation Changes using
Satellite Methods

by

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**Research Council of Norway
Contract N° 200408**

NERSC Technical Report No. 333

31 January 2014

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Introduction

The Arctic plays a fundamental role in the climate system and shows significant sensitivity to anthropogenic climate forcing and the ongoing climate change. Accelerated changes in the Arctic are already observed, including elevated air and ocean temperatures, declines of the summer sea ice extent and sea ice thickness influencing the albedo and CO₂ exchange, melting of the Greenland Ice Sheet and increased thawing of surrounding permafrost regions. In turn, the hydrological cycle in the high latitude and Arctic is expected to undergo changes although to date it is challenging to accurately quantify this. Moreover, changes in the temperature and salinity of surface waters in the Arctic Ocean and Nordic Seas may also influence the flow of dense water through the Denmark Strait, which are found to be a precursor for changes in the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) with a lead time of around 10 years (Hawkins and Sutton, 2008). Evidently changes in the Arctic and surrounding seas have far reaching influences on regional and global environment and climate variability, thus emphasizing the need for advanced quantitative understanding of the ocean circulation and transport variability in the high latitude and Arctic Ocean. In this respect this study combines *in-situ* data with coupled sea ice - ocean models, radar altimeter data and the latest GOCE-based geoid in order to estimate and assess the quality, usefulness and validity of the new satellite data and methods for studies of the ocean circulation and transport estimates in the Nordic Seas and Arctic Ocean.

The SATICE project also ensured the first high-rate, high-precision positioning experiment on sea ice in the Arctic Ocean. SATICE is consisting of an array of five polar GPS buoys operating simultaneously. Each buoy collects continuous GPS data while drifting on sea ice. Data from each buoy is streamed over a satellite link to a central computer on the Internet in near real time, where they are processed to estimate the time-varying buoy positions. SATICE positioning goal is sub-hourly, sub-decimeter precision in three dimensions over buoy separations spanning from intra-floe to pan-Arctic scales.

Main Goal

The overarching goal of the SATICE project is three fold:

- (i) develop and prove novel satellite based methods for observing sea ice and ocean dynamic topography;
- (ii) improve coupled ice-ocean-atmospheric models for the Arctic Ocean;
- (iii) improve the representation of tides in these models.

To accomplish this, the main objective is to develop high-precision GPS ice-drifting buoys (hpGPS buoy) to collect in situ data for testing and validation of the models and improve the ice/water dynamic description (<http://satice.icm.csic.es>). A secondary component of the hpGPS buoy is the incorporation of technology that has recently been developed at SAMS as part of a UK funded project to obtain the mass balance of sea ice over an annual cycle. Through a novel combination of thermistors and heating elements these buoys measure the temperature of the lower atmosphere, ice and upper ocean as well as defining the interfaces between the atmosphere, snow, ice and the ocean. From the evolution of these time-series data the mass balance can be monitored remotely. To date three of these buoys have been deployed in the

Arctic, one in the Baltic and six in the Antarctic. However, as the operation periods of these hpGPS buoys have been rather short with insufficient availability of long time-series the ability to fully reach the goals have been limited.

The testing of the high-precision GPS ice-drifting (hpGPS) bouys (see Figure 1) have shown promising capabilities but non-frequent deployment and lack of long-duration time series have limited the data collection of, for instance, sea ice freeboard, sea ice thickness and tidal elevation change and hence inter-comparison and validation against other data and models. Two new SATICE buoys were deployed at 82°N on August 13 2012. On the other hand, a permit with the Russians to deploy a buoy as part of their winter ice camp near the North Pole could not be closed in time.

In order to continue the work in WP4 where NERSC has a contributing role it was agreed that 135 KNOK should be transferred to 2013. This will allow the RCN funded SATICE project to continue the international collaboration managed by Dr. Pedro Elosegui (CSIC, Spain) under the European Science Foundation PolarCLIMATE project where the other partners include Rene Fosberg (DTU, Denmark), Rudiger Gerdes (AWI, Germany), Peter Wadhams (LOV, France) and Jeremy Wilkinson (SAMS, UK).

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the measurement system integrated in the high-precision GPS ice-drifting bouys (hpGPS buoy). Note that the sea level and the snow depth measurements together with the pre-determined length of the pipe are necessary to be able to calculate the freeboard.

Main results and Achievements

Changes in the dynamic topography and ocean circulation between the northern Atlantic Ocean and the Arctic Ocean result from variations in the atmospheric forcing

field and convective overturning combined with changes in freshwater runoff and their pathways, mean sea level, sea ice deformation and water mass transformation. Accurate knowledge of the ocean transport variability together with understanding of the water mass transformations within and across these regions is highly needed to quantify changes in the overturning circulation with acceptable uncertainty. The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation is, among other factors, influenced by: - variations in the upper ocean and sea ice interaction; - ice sheet mass changes and their effect on the regional sea level change; - changes in freshwater fluxes and pathways; and – variability in the large scale atmospheric pressure field. For instance, changes in the pathways of the freshwater from the Eurasian runoff forced by shifts in the Arctic Oscillation can lead to increased trapping of freshwater in the Arctic Ocean as presented by Morison et al. (2012) that, in turn, may alter the thermohaline circulation in the sub-Arctic Seas.

The ESA GOCE satellite High level Processing Facility (HPF) delivers the Level-2 global gravity model from which geoid heights can be determined [Johannessen et al., 2003; Bingham et al., 2011]. The mean dynamic topography (MDT) which is simply the difference between the altimeter-based mean sea surface height (MSS) and the GOCE-based geoid (G) (both referenced to the same ellipsoid), can therefore now be determined with new and unprecedented accuracy better than ≈ 3 cm at 100 km spatial resolution (Bruinsma et al., 2013). In comparison to the use of the reference geoid obtained from the Earth Gravitational Model 2008 (EGM2008) this yields a factor 2 improvement in the MDT at this spatial resolution. However, this accuracy is not necessarily applicable to the Arctic Ocean and the neighboring sub-Arctic seas due to presence of sea ice, lack of Jason altimeter coverage and shorter dominant spatial scales.

Based on 12 months of GOCE data acquired in the time interval 1 November 2009 to 14 April 2011 the GOCE-based MDT for the high latitude and Arctic Ocean has been determined for the period 1993-2009 (Johannessen et al., 2013) as shown in Figure 2 with a spatial resolution of about 100 km. The total MDT elevation range reaches about 0.9 m from the high in the Arctic Ocean to the low in the sub-polar gyre in the North Atlantic. The regional shape of the MDT with the orientation of the dominant slopes in the different sub-domains reveals the presence of the circulation pathways in: (i) the sub-polar gyre south of Greenland; (ii) the inflow of Atlantic Water respectively between Iceland and the Faroe Islands and between the Faroe and Shetland Islands; (iii) the continuous northward flowing Atlantic Water towards the Arctic Ocean; (iv) the southward flowing East Greenland Current; (v) the Beaufort Gyre; and (vi) the transpolar drift in the Arctic Ocean.

The MDT in the Arctic Ocean may display some characteristic features that are caused by problems in the data coverage. Both the GOCE data and the altimeter data do not cover the Arctic Ocean entirely, so within 300-400 km from the pole the data coverage is insufficient to calculate a reliable MDT. Also, the presence of sea ice may hamper the computation of the MSS and hence the MDT. Though care is taken to avoid erroneous data some of the data that have been used to calculate the MSS may represent the top of the sea ice flow rather than the sea surface. Especially off the coasts of the Canadian Archipelago and northern Greenland the high values of the GOCE MDT may be caused by the influence of the permanent and thick sea ice cover.

Figure 2. Mean dynamic topography (MDT) derived from the GOCE gradiometer data (release 3) and altimetry (from 1993-2009) with a spatial resolution of about 100 km. Colour bar is in units of meter.

The Arctic Ocean displays an elevation change reaching up to about 0.45 m associated with the high in the Beaufort Gyre, and with the corresponding dominant orientation of the slope mostly aligned from Siberia to the northern shores of Greenland. According to Steele and Ermold (2006) the dynamic height in the Arctic Ocean is predominantly influenced by salinity. In the Nordic Seas the general shape of the MDT favors the cyclonic circulation pattern displaying steepest MDT slopes of 0.4 m/100 km between the Faroe and Shetland Islands, along the northwest coast of Norway and in the northern part of the East Greenland Current. In comparison the slope across the Gulf Stream reaches 1 m/100 km. This spatial pattern in the MDT agrees well with the spatial pattern in the mean steric height derived from hydrographic data (Nilsen et al., 2008) for the period 1950-2010 (Figure 3) as fully shown in Johannessen et al (2013).

Figure 3. (a) MDT derived from combined GOCE and altimetry, (b) steric height derived from the in-situ hydrographic database. The color bars represent the height contours in unit of cm. Note the different colour ranges.

In view of these promising GOCE-based results they are also providing a new opportunity for inter-comparison and validation of:

- (a) forced coupled ocean-ice-models and re-analyses fields;
- (b) fully coupled ocean-atmosphere models that have delivered their fields to CMIP5.

Coupled ocean-ice-models and re-analyses fields. The three coupled sea ice – ocean models in general reproduce comparable overall spatial structure of the MDT in the Arctic Ocean, the Nordic Seas and the North Atlantic, notably the high in the Beaufort Gyre and the depressions in the Nordic Seas and the Sub-polar Gyre. The model highs in the Beaufort Gyre are circular and located towards the deep Canadian Basin with decreasing values towards the Eurasian Basin, providing an elevation difference of 0.5-0.6 m. The MICOM-field, however, has a gyre that extends into the Eurasian Basin, that, in turn, leads to incorrect transpolar drift. In comparison, the GOCE-based elevated feature in the Beaufort Sea is shifted more towards the Canadian Archipelago, while the total elevation difference remains the same. This shift in location is in agreement with the recent findings by Kwok et al., (2011) and Morrison et al., (2012). Overall the MDT patterns in the model fields for the Arctic Ocean are in reasonably good agreement with the GOCE-based MDT map.

In the central domain of the Norwegian-Greenland Seas the suppression of the MDT in the three models corresponding to the large-scale cyclonic circulation pattern with the northward flowing Norwegian-North Atlantic Current (NwAC) and the southward flowing East Greenland Current (EGC) is consistent in location, although the magnitudes and spatial structures of the suppression differ between the models as well as in comparison to the GOCE-based MDT pattern. The largest suppression is found in the ATL model with a minimum deviation from the average of -0.6 m in the northern Greenland Sea being almost twice as large as in the GOCE-based MDT located in the same area. Similar tendencies are seen in the Sub-polar Gyre, although the difference in the minima between the ATL model and the GOCE-based MDT now is reduced by a factor of 2.

The most prominent discrepancies are the mismatch in the MDT along the Canadian Archipelago and northern Greenland coast, and the models lack of higher elevations associated with the spread of AW in the Norwegian Sea, notably around the Vøring Plateau. The former might be related to presence of thicker multi-year sea ice that could influence the estimation of the MSS and thus the GOCE-based MDT. Kwok and Morrison (2011) did not reveal this particular high in the MDT confined to the coastal region from IceSAT data. The latter is related to the topographic steering of the baroclinic western branch of the NwAC (Nilsen and Nilsen, 2007), as well as eddy transport of buoyant waters from the slope branch of the NwAC into the Lofoten Basin (Rossby et al, 2009), which both are challenging to model. Furthermore, although totally lacking the broadness of the NwAC, the ATL model is the only model with the doming of the densest waters of the Nordic Seas placed in the correct basin, the Greenland Basin.

These differences in magnitude and spatial structure of the model and GOCE-based MDTs imply different strengths and orientations of the slopes in the MDT. In turn, the

mean surface geostrophic currents are expected to have discrepancies that subsequently will lead to differences in the estimation of the associated transport of water masses. The large-scale cyclonic surface circulation regime is well reproduced in all three fields (Figure 4). However, while the strongest mean surface currents of the inflowing Atlantic Water to the Norwegian Sea reaching nearly 0.2 m/s are derived from the GOCE MDT, the inflow in the other two surface current fields is clearly weaker with maximum speed not much more than 0.10 m/s. Moreover, it is only the GOCE-based surface geostrophic current that reveal distinct expressions of cyclonic circulation in the Greenland Basin, Norwegian Basin and Iceland Sea, as well as the broadening of the NwAC over the Vøring Plateau and in the Lofoten Basin, i.e. signs of a proper western (baroclinic) branch of the northward flowing Atlantic Water. From this intercomparison and assessment it is therefore evident that the GOCE-based geoid provides a reliable representation of the MDT and mean ocean surface circulation in the Nordic Seas. This is also supported by the mean surface circulation pattern derived from the climatology of the surface drifter data.

Figure 4. Inter-comparison of models and GOCE based mean absolute surface geostrophic velocity from: (a) HYCOM model from 1993-2010; (b) the ATL model from 1993- 2009; (c) MICOM model from 1993-2007; and (d) GOCE. The color bars are in cm/s. The 3 black dotted lines marks the position of the Island-Faroe Ridge section, the Faroe-Shetland Channel section and the Svinøy section.

Coupled ocean-atmosphere models from CMIP5. The quality of the existing reanalyses and simulation fields of the annual trends in mean sea level change from the three Global Climate Models (NorESM, Hadley and IPSL that all have delivered to CMIP4) is intercompared to the reprocessed annual trend in mean sea level derived from reprocessed satellite altimeter data at a spatial resolution from 25 to 50 km.

The altimeter data reveals some distinct features of elevated trend in sea level rise notably: in the Beaufort Sea; in the Norwegian Sea; in the Sub-Polar gyre; and in the North East Atlantic south of the Iceland-Faroe ridge. The signal in the Beaufort basin around 6.5-7 mm/year has also been reported by Morison et al., (2012), although the orientation is slightly different in the latter two reports. Along the west coast of Norway Richter et al, (2012) recently reported a sea level rise of about 2-3 mm/year for the period 1960-2010 using long time series from tide gauge data. In comparison the trend derived in reprocessed altimeter data is also about 3-4 mm/year but only from 1993-2011.

Moreover, in the Lofoten basin of the Norwegian Sea the elevated feature of around 6-7 mm/year as detected in the altimeter product compares rather well with the trend recovered from in-situ hydrographic observations. This is documented in Figure 5 below and reveals that the steric height signal centered in the Lofoten Basin reaches a mean trend around 4.5 to 5.5 mm/year. The discrepancy might thus be explained by the barotropic contribution to the mean sea level trend. No evidence of a trend is observed in the steric field in the Greenland Sea, while the trend south of Island is very clear and in reasonable agreement with the altimeter based trend.

Figure 5. The mean spatial trend in sea level rise from the altimeter (left) and in-situ steric height (right) for the period 1993-2011.

All in all these comparable pattern in the trend of the sea level change observed from altimetry and in-situ data suggest that the refined altimeter based extraction of the mean sea surface (MSS) and its change for the period 1993 to 2011 are highly reliable. In turn, this implies that we can have confidence in the combined use of the GOCE geoid and altimeter based MSS in these seas, from which also the mean dynamic topography, mean surface geostrophic current and absolute geostrophic

current are derived. These partly validated reprocessed sea level trend data therefore also becomes highly valuable regarding assessment of ocean models, both fully coupled GCM and forced ocean models.

A first look at the three GCMs reveals large individual differences in the trend of sea level change, both regarding the overall trend as well as in its regional characteristic changes. In comparison to the altimeter based signals the NorESM simulations (1° resolution) yield the best agreement. In contrast the Hadley simulations (1° resolution north of 30° N) reveal too large and uniform rise in the Nordic Seas and on the shelves in the Arctic Ocean, while the IPSL simulations (2° resolution away from equator) reveal a too large rise in the central deeper area of the Arctic Ocean basin.

The evidence of the trend in the sea level rise in the Sub-Polar gyre, in the northeast Atlantic Ocean south of the Iceland-Faroe ridge, in the Lofoten basin of the Norwegian Sea and in the Beaufort Gyre depicted in NorESM are clearly in more favorable agreement with the altimeter based sea level trend. This is further documented by the comparison of trends along the selected transects at 58° N in the North Atlantic and at 70° N in the Nordic Seas. The Nordic Sea transect (Figure 6) was selected to cross the sea level rise in the Lofoten basin as depicted in the altimeter and in-situ hydrographic trends.

Figure 6. Comparison of the observed sea level trend (mm/year) from the altimeter data (black) to the GCM simulated trends, notably NoreESM (blue), HAGEM2 (red) and IPSL (green) for the west-east transect along 70° N in the Nordic Seas.

The comparison of these transects in the Nordic Seas reveal that the NorESM trends agree rather well with the altimeter except across the Lofoten basin where the sea level rise is not depicted in the NorESM data. In comparison the HADGEM2 and IPSL appears out of phase along the transect with too large positive sea level trends in HADGEM2 and too large negative trends in IPSL versus the altimeter trends.

An additional inter-comparison and assessment of the sea level products is revealed in the time series of the sea level trends for part of the Lofoten Basin centered at 70°N and 10°E. The mean trend in the sea level rise for the altimeter product is about 6.1 mm/yr compared to a mean trend of about 2.8 mm/yr for the NorESM. NorESM also seems to have almost no trend from 1993 to 2005 followed by a steeper rise than in the altimeter sea level trend. Again the seasonal variability compares well in phase while discrepancies are noted in the amplitude with the NorESM signal consistently smaller than the observed. In general the spreading of the inflowing Atlantic Water in the Lofoten Basin is determined by strong topographic steering and rich abundance of mesoscale eddies which is a challenge to adequately model. This likely explains the discrepancies between the altimeter sea level and the NorESM fields.

All in all this intercomparison of the altimeter and in-situ sea level trends with the trends derived from the three GCMs is interesting and can provide evidence for how realistic the model simulations are with respect to the variability of the water masses (steric height contribution) and variability, spreading and accumulation of freshwater discharges from melting ice sheets and glaciers (mass changes). The NorESM simulations are not accounting for geoid changes and thus the contributions from the land up-lift and mass exchange cannot be assessed.

Summary

These findings add new insight of the ocean circulation and transport between the northeast Atlantic Ocean and the Arctic Ocean. They are also considered to be highly valuable for further studies of the regional sea level change in the Nordic Seas and the Arctic Ocean, notable via the contribution of the steric height and changes in the volume transport. These data and findings are also excellent for assessment and validation of model based retrieval of the mean sea level change, the MDT, the surface geostrophic current and the volume transport across selected sections and straits. Consistent use of the GOCE data for assimilation as suggested by Haines et al. (2011) might also become feasible in near future. It must be emphasized that while the inter-comparison appears acceptable in some oceanic regions they are less satisfactory in other regions. This emphasizes the need for further studies and analyses in which the data from the high-rate, high-precision positioning sea ice buoys will become highly valuable.

In summary the following key results are highlighted:

- (i) Distinct features of sea level rise are found in the Sub-Polar Gyre and the Lofoten basin that are also partly simulated in the general coupled climate NorESM.
- (ii) New knowledge of the shape and spatial pattern of the MDT is derived at a spatial resolution of around 100 km and with an accuracy of around 5 cm which is superior to previous existing MDTs for this region.
- (iii) Combined with the steric height estimated from hydrographic data the pure barotropic contribution to the MDT shows distinct features in consistence with

known existence of deep barotropic circulations in the central regions of the Norwegian - and Greenland Seas.

- (iv) Comparison of the surface geostrophic current, inverted from the new GOCE based MDT, to existing independent surface velocity calculations derived from combined altimeter data, in-situ observations and gravity field models is in favourable support to the GOCE-derived geoid and MDT.
- (v) The transport estimates, both in the mean and seasonal signals, are also favouring the combined use of the GOCE-based surface geostrophic current and hydrographic data.
- (vi) New understanding of the relationship between the MDT, the mean surface geostrophic current and the magnitude of the mean ocean volume transport has been derived for the seasonal variability with regards to the inflow of Atlantic Water to the Norwegian Sea at the Svinøy section.

Moreover, as gravity measurements provide an integrated view of the mass variations, their interpretation in terms of mass transport is inherently multidisciplinary. Satellite gravimetry (such as combined GRACE and GOCE) is thus a vital component of a multisensor Earth observing system, which complements and relates observations of different Earth system constituents in a common and consistent global framework (Panet et al., 2012).

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